

CIGARETTE SMOKING AND HEALTH OF YOUTHS IN BIASE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study focused on cigarette smoking and health of youths in Biase Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the objectives of this study, two specific objectives were formulated thus: to identify the effect of cigarette smoking on youth mental disorder and to find out how cigarette smoking cause lung cancer among youths in Biase Local Government Area. The survey research design was adopted as the design for this study. Simple random sampling technique was used to sample respondents for the study. Findings of the analysis revealed that there exists significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables for this study. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended amongst others that: governments and health organizations must continue to enforce policies that restrict cigarette advertisements, limit youth access to tobacco products, and implement graphic warning labels on cigarette packages to highlight the dangers of smoking.

Keywords: Cigarette, Smoking, Health, Youths, Mental Disorder

INTRODUCTION

Cigarette smoking is the inhalation of smoke from burning tobacco, which contains harmful chemicals such as nicotine, tar, carbon, monoxide, and formaldehyde. Cigarette smoking is one of the leading causes of preventable death worldwide, and its health risks are well-documented. Smoking exposes individuals to over 7,000 chemicals, many of which are toxic or carcinogenic (WHO, 2015). These chemicals include nicotine, tar, carbon monoxide, formaldehyde, and ammonia. The long-term use of cigarettes is strongly associated with a range of serious health

conditions, including lung cancer, heart disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and stroke. Additionally, smoking is a major risk factor for respiratory infections, reduced immunity, and reproductive issues. Cigarette smoking ranges from experimentation to chronic smoking disorder. Cigarette smoking generally puts the youths at risk of short-term problems, such as accidents, fights, unwanted sexual activity, and overdose. In modern society, cigarette smoking is an easy way for youths to satisfy the normal developmental need to take risks and seek thrills.

Globally, the World Health Organization (WHO, 2019) estimates that cigarette smoking kills nearly seven million people annually and 100 million deaths have been recorded over the course of the 20th century. More than six million of the deaths are the result of direct cigarette use while close to 900,000 deaths are the result of non-smokers being exposed to second-hand smoking. Unless urgent action is taken, the annual death toll could rise to more than eight million by 2023 (WHO, 2019) while the global burden of NCDs is estimated to rise by 17 percent will be experienced in the African region (WHO 2018).

According to National Health Surveys (2017), the rates of cigarette smoking among youths in Nigeria fell dramatically in the 1990s and 2000s and continue to decline. The Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) survey reported that in 2019, about 5.7% of youths reported current cigarette use (smoked in the previous 30 days), which was down from 28.3% in 2005 and from 7.6% in 2018. Only about 2% of youths reported smoking every day. The majority of adults who smoke cigarettes begin smoking during adolescence. To Bernard (2018), if adolescents do not try cigarettes before age 19, they are very unlikely to become smokers as adults.

Cigarette smoking has long been recognized as a major public health issue across the globe, with devastating consequences for individuals and communities, in Cross River State. Emaku (2019) noted that the single strongest risk factor for youths smoking cigarette is having parents who smoke. Other risk factors often associated with starting cigarette smoking during childhood include: Peers and role models (such as celebrities) who smoke; Poor school performance; Other high-risk behavior' (such as excessive dieting, particularly among girls; physical fighting and drunk driving, particularly among boys; or use of alcohol or other substances); Poor problem-solving abilities; Availability of cigarettes and Poor self-esteem. Ekwodo (2019), further noted that adolescents may also use tobacco in other forms. About 3.5% of high school students use smokeless tobacco, and this rate has declined over the past 10 years. Smokeless tobacco can be chewed, (chewing tobacco), placed between the lower lip and gum (dipping tobacco, or dip), or inhaled into the nose (snuff). Electronic cigarettes (e-cigarettes, e-cigs, vapes) are battery-operated devices that use heat to turn a liquid into a vapor that can be inhaled. These liquids typically contain nicotine, which is the active ingredient in tobacco, or tetrahydrocannabinol (THC), which is the active ingredient in marijuana. Both nicotine and THC are addictive. Electronic cigarettes initially entered the market as nicotine cessation devices for adult smokers. They have since morphed into "vapes" which are highly attractive to and have become increasingly popular among adolescents over the past several years, especially among

adolescents of middle and upper social and economic status. Current e-cigarette use (nicotine vaping, not counting other substances) among 12th graders increased markedly from 4.5% in 2013 to 25.5% in 2019. About 45.6% of youths have tried e-cigarettes (nicotine and other substances) (Ofcm, Uttah, Etim, Aycni, Emeka, Ewuru & Etta, 2024).

In Biase, a local government area in Cross River State, Nigeria, the problem of cigarette smoking among youths has become increasingly prevalent, leading to alarming health risks. For youths, the risks associated with smoking are even more concerning (Nnana & Isaac, 2024). Adolescents who begin smoking at an early age are more likely to develop lifelong addictions, which makes it difficult for them to quit in the future. Smoking during adolescence can interfere with lung development, leading to reduced lung function in adulthood. Moreover, young smokers are at a higher risk of developing mental health issues such as anxiety and depression. This age group is particularly vulnerable to the addictive properties of nicotine, as their brains are still developing. Richard (2018); Nnana, Adie, Omini & Runyi (2024).

In Biase, where there is a growing prevalence of smoking among youths, the long-term health consequences could severely impact the future well-being of an entire generation. Without intervention, the youth in Biase may face an increasing burden of smoking-related diseases, resulting in reduced quality of life, premature deaths, and higher healthcare costs for the community (Tangban, Nnana & Udousoro, 2024). Smoking increases the risk of heart attack, lung cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), including lung cancer and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Several factors contribute to the rising rates of cigarette smoking among youths in Biase. These include social, economic, and environmental influences, as well as a lack of awareness about the dangers of smoking (Nnana, Isaac & Blessing, 2023). One of the most significant factors influencing smoking among youths in Biase is peer pressure. Adolescents are often highly influenced by their friends and social circles, and smoking is sometimes perceived as a way to fit in, appear "cool," or demonstrate maturity. The desire to belong to a group can outweigh the awareness of the health risks involved in smoking. Many young people in Biase may not fully understand the health risks associated with smoking (Stephen, 2019).

According to Sharmark (2019), cigarettes are often easily accessible and affordable in Biase, making it easier for youths to start smoking. The availability of cheap or even smuggled cigarettes in local markets and shops exacerbates the problem. Without stringent regulations or enforcement of laws restricting the sale of tobacco products to minors, youths can easily purchase cigarettes. In some cases, smoking among youths in Biase is a learned behavior, passed down from family members. If parents or older siblings smoke, youths may view smoking as a normal behavior and may be more likely to start smoking themselves. He furthered that the absence of strong parental guidance or supervision can further exacerbate the problem. Adolescence is a period of emotional and psychological development, and many youths in Biase may turn to smoking as a coping mechanism for stress, peer pressure, or mental health issues. (Nnana, Olofu, & Runyi, 2024). Unfortunately, nicotine can create a temporary feeling of relief or euphoria.

which reinforces the habit. However, this short-term benefit is overshadowed by the long-term health risks (Sharmark, 2019). This study intends to assess cigarette smoking and health of youths in Biase Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Cigarette smoking is a well-established global health hazard, contributing significantly to the morbidity and mortality rates worldwide. In the context of Biase Local Government, a region in Cross River State, Nigeria, cigarette smoking remains a prevalent practice among certain segments of the population, despite increasing awareness of its detrimental health effects. It is a leading cause of preventable diseases such as lung cancer, heart disease, chronic respiratory conditions, and stroke. Despite the well-documented health risks, smoking continues to be prevalent in many regions, including Biase, where both young and older adults engage in the habit (Tangban & Nnana, 2024).

In Biase, as in many other parts of Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa, smoking is not only a health issue but also a social one. Cultural norms, stress factors, peer pressure, and a lack of awareness contribute to the persistence of smoking in the area. Although statistics on smoking prevalence in Biase specifically are limited, tobacco use has been identified as an increasing trend in urban and rural communities across Nigeria. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2019), around 4.5% of Nigerian adults currently smoke, with a noticeable rise in the number of young smokers. Cigarette smoking causes a wide range of immediate and long-term health effects, many of which impact the cardiovascular, respiratory, and nervous systems.

Smoking is a major cause of heart disease and stroke. In Biase, where there is an increasing adoption of sedentary lifestyles, smoking exacerbates the risk of developing hypertension, heart attacks, and other cardiovascular diseases. Nicotine, an addictive substance in cigarettes, raises blood pressure and causes blood vessels to constrict, leading to reduced blood flow and increased strain on the heart. One of the most significant health impacts of smoking is its detrimental effect on the lungs. The inhalation of toxic substances in cigarette smoke damages the respiratory system, increasing the risk of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), emphysema, and lung cancer. In Biase, where the prevalence of diseases like tuberculosis (TB) and pneumonia are already a concern, smoking further weakens the immune system, making individuals more susceptible to infections. Smoking is the leading cause of lung cancer, which is one of the deadliest forms of cancer worldwide. The toxic chemicals in cigarette smoke also contribute to other cancers, including those of the throat, mouth, pancreas, and bladder. With the growing trend in smoking among the youth in Biase, the region may see an increase in cancer cases in the coming decades.

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Nicotine, the primary addictive component of cigarettes, causes dependence and can lead to psychological withdrawal symptoms. For many smokers in Biase, this addiction complicates efforts to quit smoking, perpetuating the cycle of harm. Moreover, smoking has been linked to mental health disorders such as depression and anxiety. The mental health challenges exacerbated by smoking further strain the healthcare system in Biase, where mental health services may already be limited (Ofem, 2023). Certain groups within the population are more vulnerable to the harmful effects of smoking. Women, children, and those living in poverty in Biase may experience disproportionate health risks associated with smoking. Women who smoke during pregnancy put their unborn children at risk of preterm birth, low birth weight, and developmental issues. Second-hand smoke also poses significant risks to children, who are more susceptible to respiratory illnesses such as asthma and bronchitis. In Biase, where maternal and child health challenges are prominent, smoking adds to the burden of preventable health complications. In Biase, as in many parts of Nigeria, smoking is more prevalent among individuals from lower socioeconomic background (Nnana, Enobong, Anyang, Cecilia, & Beauty, 2023). This demographic may have less access to healthcare services and awareness about the risks of smoking, leading to higher rates of smoking-related diseases. The financial strain of purchasing cigarettes also diverts resources away from other health and family needs.

The socioeconomic burden of cigarette smoking in Biase is significant. Smoking-related diseases strain the healthcare system, leading to increased healthcare costs. Additionally, the loss of productivity due to illness and early death from smoking-related diseases impacts the local economy. The environmental consequences of smoking, including cigarette litter and the harmful effects of tobacco fanning on the ecosystem, also add to the social cost. It is at this instance that this study is spout up to harness cigarette smoking and health of youths in Biase Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Literature review

Substance abuse and youth mental health behaviour

Cigarette smoking has long been recognized as a significant public health issue, contributing to various physical diseases, such as lung cancer, cardiovascular disease, and respiratory illnesses. However, in recent years, there has been growing concern over the impact of smoking on mental health, particularly among young people. As the adolescent years are a critical period for brain

development and mental health, the relationship between cigarette smoking and youth mental disorders has become an important area of research (Blecher & Ross. 2017).

According to Brain (2019), smoking is often seen as a coping mechanism by many young people, with adolescents and teenagers turning to cigarettes in an attempt to deal with stress, emotional problems, or peer pressure. While smoking might initially provide a temporary sense of relief or relaxation, the long-term effects can be detrimental to mental health. Fowles and Dybing (2016), noted that for many young people, cigarette smoking may act as a trigger for the onset of mental disorders, especially when combined with other risk factors such as genetic predisposition, environmental stress, and social challenges. Schools, communities, and healthcare providers play a vital role in offering resources and support to youth who may be struggling with both smoking and mental health issues (Nnana. 2023).

According to Jackson (2018), programs that focus on building resilience, coping skills, and emotional regulation can help reduce the likelihood of young people turning to cigarettes as a means of managing stress. Early intervention is also important as it can prevent the development of nicotine dependence and mental health disorders from becoming more severe. For those who already smoke, offering counseling, cognitive-behavioral therapy, and other forms of mental health support help address the underlying issues contributing to both smoking and mental health challenges. The relationship between cigarette smoking and youth mental health is complex and concerning. While smoking may offer temporary relief from stress and anxiety, its long-term effects can contribute to the development of mental disorders such as depression and anxiety. Furthermore, the addictive nature of nicotine can exacerbate existing mental health conditions and create a vicious cycle that is difficult to break. As such, addressing both smoking and mental health issues in young people requires a comprehensive approach that involves prevention, early intervention, and ongoing support. By promoting mental well-being and offering resources to help youth quit smoking, society can mitigate the negative impact of smoking on the mental health of future generations (Nnana. Isaac & Blessing. 2023).

Cigarette smoking and lung cancer among youth

Cigarette smoking has long been recognized as a leading cause of preventable diseases, with lung cancer being one of the most severe consequences of long-term smoking. While the link between cigarette smoking and lung cancer is well-established in adults, the growing prevalence of smoking among adolescents raises concerns about the potential long-term impact on their health. Youth are particularly vulnerable to the harmful effects of smoking, as their bodies and lungs are still developing, making them more susceptible to both immediate and long-term health problems (Jackson, 2018).

According to Park (2017), lung cancer, a leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, is predominantly caused by long-term exposure to carcinogens found in cigarette smoke. Cigarettes contain more than 7,000 chemicals, many of which are toxic and can cause cellular damage. Among these, tar, nicotine, and carbon monoxide are especially harmful to the lungs. The

carcinogenic properties of tobacco smoke lead to genetic mutations in lung cells, which can eventually result in the uncontrollable growth of abnormal cells, forming tumors. Moreover, the younger a person is when they begin smoking, the more likely they are to become addicted to nicotine, which leads to prolonged exposure to these toxic substances (Mendez, Alshangccty & Warner, 2016). According to Neal (2023), the age at which an individual starts smoking plays a crucial role in determining their risk of developing lung cancer.

Social disorganization theory (SDT)

Unlike the social learning theory, the social disorganization theory (SOT) proposed by Shaw and McKay (1931) explains and predicts deviant behaviours as being influenced by basic social factors, such as differences in economic status, residential mobility and physical nature of neighbourhood in which heterogeneity manifests. Rather than the individual-based explanation of the social learning perspective, the theorists assumed that deviant behavioural manifestation are common place in large complex societies. They believe that as the societal structure and contexts process from simple to complex nature, deviation and non-conformity to social norms and values increase, these behaviours become stronger as the limits of social interaction extend to local, face-to-face to large human settlements of cities and urban life where the social consequences of various forms of personal conduct have become discernable. In this process of societal transformation, the extended family and close-knit neighbourhood relationship and interaction, which enhance conformity relatively, disappear. In its place, individual's indifferent attitudes to actions that surround the urban life become pre-eminent.

The social disorganization theory lays the background to the idea that the closer individuals are bonding into an informal network of social relationship, the greater the degree of conformity. When individuals are in a heterogeneous environment where there is variance in economic and social values, which creates conflict situation. This theory therefore predicts conditions where anti-social behaviour are most likely to thrive due to the opportunities and lapses created by structural heterogeneity of values and consequently disorganization. When there is cultural heterogeneity, conflict in values and rules, the social control mechanisms will also be in conflict, weak and minimally functional. Apparently, individuals will deviate from the norms because the rules in existence may neither be too loose or too harsh in application.

Methodology

The survey design was adopted for this study. A survey design is used to access and predict the views, reactions or standings of a large number of people on a limited topic like cigarette smoking and health of youths in Biase Local Government Area. Under survey design, the researcher develops a list of questions and presents them in a standard way to each participant typically using either the interview or questionnaire.

Biase Local Government Area (LGA) is located in the southeastern part of Cross River State, Nigeria. It is one of the IX LGAs in the state and is known for its rich cultural heritage, scenic landscapes, and diverse communities. The headquarters of Biase LGA is situated in the town of

Akpct Central, which serves as the administrative hub of the area. Biase LGA is bordered by several other I.GAs in dross River State, including Akamkpa to the north and Odukpani to the west.

The major rivers in Biase include the Cross River, which runs along its boundary with Akamkpa. and the Calabar River, which provides water sources for many local communities. Agriculture is the mainstay of the economy in Biase LG A. The fertile soil and favorable climate allow for the cultivation of a w ide range of crops, which are essential for both local consumption and trade. Crops such as yam, cassava, cocoyam, plantains, maize, and cocoa arc grown extensively. Additionally, fishing along the river systems and animal husbandry are common economic activities. The population of the study area is one hundred and sixty-nine thousand, one hundred and eighty-three (169,183) as projected by the National Population Commission (NPC, 2006). This population comprises of both men. women and children in the study area. The sample for this study was drawn from the total population of the study area which is 169,183. In analysing the data, each hypothesis w ill be tested using the Chi-square Statistical tool.

Findings

Demographic data of respondents were presented in simple percentage, w hile the stated hypotheses were analysed using chi-square statistical tool.

Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Sex		
Male	280	70
Female	120	30
Total	400	100
Age		
18-21	196	49
22-28	97	24
29-35	68	17
36 and above	46	12
Total	400	100
Educational qualification		
Primary	0	0
Secondary	130	33
Tertiary	224	20
Others	46	13
Total	400	100
Marital status		
Single	278	69
Married	101	25

Separated	10	3
Divorced	8	2
Widow	3	1
Widower	0	0
Total	400	100

Source: Fieldwork. 2025.

The distribution of respondent based on gender shows that, out of the total respondents of 400, 280 respondents representing 70% were male, while 120 respondents representing 30% were female. The male folks were more in the study because they were readily available to provide needed information on the questionnaire. The above table shows that 196 respondents representing 49% were between the ages 18-21 years. 97 respondents (14.25%) were between the ages of 22-27 years. 68 respondents (17%) were between the ages of 29-35 years, while 40 respondents (10%) were 36 years and above. Respondents who fall within the age range of 18-21 were more in the study because they had more knowledge and are greatly affected by substance abuse in the area.

The table further shows that respondents who had FSLC did not participate in the study. 130 respondents representing 32.5% were secondary school education holders. 224 (56%) had tertiary education, while 46 respondents (11.5%) held other qualifications. This shows that respondents who had tertiary education were more in the study because they have broad knowledge about the effect of substance abuse on health. Variables based on marital status of respondents reveals that 278 respondents representing 69.5% were single. 101 respondents (25.2%) were married. 10 respondents (2.5%) were separated. 8 respondents (2%) were divorced, while only 3 respondents (0.75%) were widowed. Single respondents were more in the study because they mostly practice substance abuse.

Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis one:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between cigarette smoking and youth mental disorder in Biase Local Government Area

H₁: There is a significant relationship between cigarette smoking and youth mental disorder in Biase Local Government Area; To test this hypothesis, responses of respondents based on the variables on the questionnaire was used.

Table 2: Relationship between cigarette smoking and youth's mental disorder

Responses	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
Yes	185	150	335	83.75
No	35	20	65	16.25
Total	220	180	400	100

Source: Fieldwork. 2025.

Table 3: Chi square computational table of hypothesis one

Cells	i'	-	(o-e) ²	fc
185	184.025	0.75	0.5625	3.0529
150	150.75	0.75	0.5625	3.7313
35	35.75	0.75	0.5625	0.0157
30	29.25	0.75	0.5625	0.0192
Total	400		6.82	

Calculated chi-square value = 6.82

Tabulated chi-square value = 3.84

Significant level - 0.05

Decision rule:

The rule states that, if the calculated chi-square value is greater than the tabulated or critical value, then we accept the alternative hypothesis, otherwise we reject it.

Analysis:

In the computation in table 3, it shows that calculated chi-square value is greater than the tabulated chi-square value i.e. $6.82 > 3.84$, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant relationship between cigarette smoking and youth mental disorder.

Hypothesis two:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between cigarette smoking and lungs cancer among youths in Biase Local Government Area

H₁: There is a significant relationship between cigarette smoking and lungs cancer among youths in Biase Local Government Area. To test this hypothesis, responses of respondents based, on the variables on the questionnaire was used.

Table 4: Relationship between cigarette smoking and lungs cancer among youths

Responses	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
Yes	165	130	295	74
No	55	40	105	26
Total	220	180	400	100

Source: Fieldwork. 2025.

Table 5: Chi -square computational table of hypothesis two

Cells	o	e	(o-e) ²	(o-e) ² / e
165	165.25	-0.25	0.0265	13.79
130	132.75	2.75	7.5625	0.06
40	41.25	1.25	1.5625	0.04
35	33.75	1.25	1.5625	0.05
15	16.5	1.5	2.25	0.14
5	13.5	1.5	2.25	0.17

Calculated chi-square value - 4.24

Tabulated chi-square value - 3.84

Significant level = 0.05

Decision rule: The rule states that, if the calculated chi-square value is greater than the tabulated or critical value, then we accept the alternative hypothesis, otherwise we reject it.

Analysis:

Question 5 shows that the calculated chi-square value is greater than the tabulated chi-square value, i.e. $4.24 > 3.84$. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, and conclude that there is a significant relationship between cigarette smoking and lungs cancer among youths.

Findings

From the analysis of hypothesis one. findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between cigarette smoking and mental disorder among youths. This is evident from the computation in table 2, which showed that the donated chi-square value was greater than the tabulated chi-square value i.e. $6.82 > 3.84$. hence the null hypotheses was rejected, while the alternate hypothesis accepted. This finding however, goes in line with the assertion of Fowles and Dybing 2016). who noted that for many young people, cigarette smoking may act as a trigger the onset of mental disorders, especially when combined with other risk factors such as genetic predisposition, environmental stress, and social challenges. Studies suggest that the earlier an individual starts smoking, the more likely they are to experience mental health problems later in life (Christiana. Nnana, Emmanuel, Lilian,. & Victor, 2022). Smoking in adolescence has been linked to an increased risk of developing anxiety disorders, depression, and other mood disorders. Furthermore, nicotine use can exacerbate pre-existing mental health conditions, making it more difficult for young people to manage their emotions and cope with life challenges.

Hypothesis two findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between cigarette smoking and lung cancer among youths. However, this is shown from the analysis computation table (table 5) that the calculated chi-square value was greater than the tabulated chi-square value, i.e. $4.24 > 3.84$: hence, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was accepted. In accordance with this findings. Park (2017). postulated that lung cancer, a leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, is predominantly caused by long-term exposure to

carcinogens Found in cigarette smoke. Cigarettes contain more than 7,000 chemicals, many of which are toxic and can cause cellular damage. Among these, tar, nicotine, and carbon monoxide are especially harmful to the lungs. The carcinogenic properties of tobacco smoke lead to genetic mutations in lung cells, which can eventually result in the uncontrollable growth of abnormal cells, forming tumors. Overtime, this damage increases the risk of developing lung cancer. While lung cancer is more common in older individuals, the damage caused by smoking begins as soon as a person starts smoking, even at a young age.

Conclusion

This study examined the cigarette smoking and health of youths in Biase Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Suffice it is to note that cigarette smoking exerts their effects by modifying biochemical or physiological processes in the brain. Cigarette smoking is a growing public health concern among youths in Biase, with far-reaching consequences for their health and well-being. The health risks associated with smoking, combined with the factors that encourage smoking behaviors, present a significant challenge for the local community. However, through targeted education, stronger regulations, and community-driven initiatives, it is possible to reduce the prevalence of smoking among youths in Biase and protect the future health of the community. With collective effort and commitment, it is possible to ensure that the next generation of youths in Biase grows up in an environment that promotes healthy, smoke-free lifestyles.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Public health campaigns, educational programs, and stricter enforcement of tobacco control policies are key to reducing smoking rates in the region.
2. Local government initiatives, in collaboration with non-governmental organizations, could raise awareness about the dangers of smoking, especially among youth and women.
3. Additionally, providing support for smoking cessation programs, such as counselling and nicotine replacement therapies, would help individuals break free from addiction.

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